

On Common Fixed-Point Results for Expansive Type Mappings in Cone Rectangular Metric Spaces

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 05 July 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: A. S. Saluja</p>	<p>In this paper, we establish common fixed-point theorems for a class of self-mappings satisfying expansive-type conditions within the framework of cone rectangular metric spaces. These generalized metric spaces incorporate a cone structure in a real Banach space, allowing for a partial ordering and broader applicability beyond traditional metric settings. We provide sufficient conditions under which such mappings admit a unique common fixed point. The presented results extend and refine several known fixed-point theorems. Additionally, examples are included to demonstrate the applicability and effectiveness of the theoretical findings in generalized metric and nonlinear analysis contexts.</p> <p>MATHEMATICS SUBJECT CLASSIFICATION (2020): Primary: 54H25; Secondary: 54E50, 47H10.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Normal cone, cone rectangular metric spaces, coincidence point, common fixed point, expansive type mappings.</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

Fixed point theorems concern maps f of a set X into itself that, under certain conditions, admit a fixed point, that is, a point $x \in X$ such that $f(x) = x$. The knowledge of the existence of fixed points has relevant applications in many branches of analysis and topology. By a contraction on a metric space (X, d) , we understand a mapping $T : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying for all $x, y \in X$: $d(Tx, Ty) \leq kd(x, y)$, where k is a real in $[0, 1)$.

Branciari [4] introduced a class of generalized (rectangular) metric spaces by replacing the triangular inequality of metric spaces with a similar one which involves four or more points instead of three points. The author also improved Banach Contraction Principle in such spaces. Recently many authors Cho, S.H.[6], Chaira K, et.al. [5] proved the existence and uniqueness of a fixed point for different types of mappings.

Azam A [2], introduced the concept of cone rectangular metric space by replacing the triangular inequality in the definition of cone metric space with a rectangular inequality and proved the Banach contraction principle on these spaces.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. [2] Let X be a non-empty set. The mapping $d_E : X \times X$ said to be cone rectangle metric space if it satisfies:

(1) $\alpha < d(x, y)$, for all $x, y \in X$ with $x \neq y$ and $d(x, y) = \alpha$ iff $x = y$;

(2) $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$, for all $x, y \in X$;

(3) $d_E(x, y) \leq d_E(x, w) + d_E(w, z) + d_E(z, y)$;

for all $x, y \in X$ and for all distinct points $u, v \in X - \{x, y\}$.

Definition 2.2. [10] Let P be a subset of a real Banach space E and α is the zero vector of E . P is said to be a cone in E if it satisfies the following properties:

(i) P is non-empty, closed and $P \neq \alpha$

(ii) $x, y \in P$ implies a $x + by \in P$, where a and b are positive real numbers;

(iii) The intersection of P and $-P$ is $\{\alpha\}$

Definition 2.3. [10] A cone P is said to be a solid cone if an interior of P is a non-empty subset of E .

Definition 2.4. [10] A partial order relation \leq with respect to a solid cone $P \subseteq E$ is defined as $x \leq y$ if $y - x \in P$, for $x, y \in E$.

Definition 2.5. [10] A cone P is called a normal cone if there is a number $k > 1$ such that for all $x, y \in X$, $\alpha \leq x \leq y$ implies that $\|x\| \leq k\|y\|$.

Definition 2.6. [2] Let (X, d_E) be a cone rectangular metric space and P be a solid cone in E : Then the sequence $\{x_n\}$ is said to converge to x if $d_E(x_n, x) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

Definition 2.7 [2] Let (X, d_E) be a cone rectangular metric space and P be a solid cone in E : Then the sequence $\{x_n\}$ is said to be Cauchy if for all $p > 0$ we have $d_E(x_n, x_{n+p}) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

Throughout this paper, P is not necessarily a normal cone in E ; the relation $x \ll y$ stands for y, x belongs to an interior of P and R denotes the set of all Real numbers.

3. MAIN RESULT

Theorem 3.1: Let (X, d_E) be a cone rectangular metric space. If the mappings P and $Q : X \rightarrow X$ satisfying the condition:

$$d_E(Px, Py) \geq \alpha_1 d_E(Qx, Qy) + \alpha_2 d_E(Px, Qx) + \alpha_3 d_E(Py, Qx) + \alpha_4 d_E(Py, Qy) \quad (3.1.1)$$

for all $x, y \in X$, where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4 \in R$ such that $\alpha_1 \geq 2$ and $0 < \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4 < \frac{1}{2}$.

If $Q(X) \subseteq P(X)$ and either of $Q(X)$ or $P(X)$ is a complete subspace of X , then Q and P have a unique coincidence point in X . Further, if Q and P are weakly compatible self-maps then they have a unique common fixed point in X .

Proof: let x_0 be an arbitrary point of X . Since $Q(X) \subseteq P(X)$ and let $x_1 \in X$ be such that $Qx_0 = Px_1$. Continuing this process, we can construct a sequence $\{\beta_n\}$ in X such that $\beta_n = Px_n = Qx_{n-1}$, for all $n \geq 1$.

$$\text{If } \beta_{n-1} = \beta_n, \text{ for some } n \geq 1 \text{ then } \beta_{n-1} = Px_{n-1} = Qx_{n-1}$$

That is P and Q have a coincidence point x_{n-1} in X . Assume $\beta_{n-1} \neq \beta_n$ for all $n \geq 1$. Then from (3.1.1)

$$\begin{aligned} d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) &= d_E(Px_{n-1}, Px_n) \geq \alpha_1 d_E(Qx_{n-1}, Qx_n) + \alpha_2 d_E(Px_{n-1}, Qx_{n-1}) + \alpha_3 d_E(Px_n, Qx_{n-1}) + \alpha_4 d_E(Px_n, Qx_n) \\ &= \alpha_1 d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) + \alpha_2 d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) + \alpha_3 d_E(\beta_n, \beta_n) + \alpha_4 d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) \\ &\geq (\alpha_1 + \alpha_4) d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) + \alpha_2 d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) \end{aligned}$$

Which implies that

$$(1 - \alpha_2) d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) \geq (\alpha_1 + \alpha_4) d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1})$$

$$\text{i.e. } (\alpha_1 + \alpha_4) d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) \leq (1 - \alpha_2) d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n)$$

$$\text{Or, } d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) \leq \frac{1 - \alpha_2}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_4} d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n)$$

Hence,

$$d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) \leq \alpha d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n), \forall n \geq 1$$

$$\text{Where, } \alpha = \frac{1 - \alpha_2}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_4} < 1 \text{ (as } \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_4 > 1$$

By induction for all $n \geq 0$

$$d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) \leq \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \quad (3.1.2)$$

Where $0 < \alpha < 1$

Using (3.1.1) and (3.1.2) and the facts that,

$$\alpha_1 \geq 2, \alpha_2 < 1, 0 < \alpha_3 < 1 \text{ and } 0 < \alpha_4 < 1$$

That is $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 > 1$ and $0 < \alpha < 1$,

We have,

$$\begin{aligned} d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_{n+1}) &= d_E(Px_{n-1}, Px_{n+1}) \\ &\geq \alpha_1 d_E(Qx_{n-1}, Qx_{n+1}) + \alpha_2 d_E(Px_{n-1}, Qx_{n-1}) + \alpha_3 d_E(Px_{n+1}, Qx_{n-1}) + \alpha_4 d_E(Px_{n+1}, Qx_{n+1}) \\ &\geq \alpha_1 d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) + \alpha_2 d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) + \alpha_3 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_n) + \alpha_4 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2}) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) &\leq d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_{n+1}) - \alpha_2 d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) - \alpha_3 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_n) - \alpha_4 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2}) \\ &\leq [d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) + d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2}, \beta_{n+1})] - \alpha_2 d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) \\ &\quad - \alpha_3 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_n) - \alpha_4 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2}) \\ &\leq d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) + (1 - \alpha_2) d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) - \alpha_3 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_n) \\ &\quad + (1 - \alpha_4) d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2}) \end{aligned}$$

Or,

$$\alpha_1 d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) - d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) \leq (1 - \alpha_2) d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) - \alpha_3 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_n) + (1 - \alpha_4) d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2})$$

$$(\alpha_1 - 1) d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) \leq (1 - \alpha_2) d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) - \alpha_3 d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_n) + (1 - \alpha_4) d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2})$$

Or,

$$d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq \left(\frac{1-\alpha_2}{\alpha_1-1}\right) d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) - \left(\frac{1-\alpha_2}{\alpha_1-1}\right) d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_n) + \left(\frac{1-\alpha_2}{\alpha_1-1}\right) d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2}) \\
 &\leq \left(\frac{1-\alpha_2}{\alpha_1-1}\right) d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) - \left(\frac{\alpha_3}{\alpha_1-1}\right) d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) + \left(\frac{1-\alpha_4}{\alpha_1-1}\right) d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2}) \\
 &\leq \left(\frac{1-\alpha_2}{\alpha_1-1}\right) \alpha^{n-1} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) - \left(\frac{\alpha_3}{\alpha_1-1}\right) \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \left(\frac{1-\alpha_4}{\alpha_1-1}\right) \alpha^{n+1} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq \left(\frac{1-\alpha_2}{\alpha_1-1} - \alpha \frac{\alpha_3}{\alpha_1-1} + \alpha^2 \frac{1-\alpha_4}{\alpha_1-1}\right) \alpha^{n-1} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq \left(\frac{1-\alpha_2}{\alpha_1-1} - \frac{\alpha_3}{\alpha_1-1} + \frac{1-\alpha_4}{\alpha_1-1}\right) \alpha \alpha^{n-1} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq \left(\frac{2-(\alpha_2+\alpha_3+\alpha_4)}{\alpha_1-1}\right) \alpha \alpha^{n-1} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq \left(\frac{1+\alpha_1}{\alpha_1-1}\right) \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) \leq \lambda \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \tag{3.1.3}$$

For $\{\beta_n\}$ we consider $d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+l})$ in two cases

If l is odd say $2p+1$, for $p \geq 1$ then by using rectangular inequality and (3.1.2)

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2p+1}) &\leq d_E(\beta_{n+2p+1}, \beta_{n+2p}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2p}, \beta_{n+2p-1}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2p-1}, \beta_n) \\
 &\leq d_E(\beta_{n+2p}, \beta_{n+2p+1}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2p-1}, \beta_{n+2p}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2p-1}, \beta_{n+2p-2}) \\
 &\quad + d_E(\beta_{n+2p-2}, \beta_{n+2p-3}) + \dots + d_E(\beta_{n+2}, \beta_{n+1}) + d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_n) \\
 &= d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+1}) + d_E(\beta_{n+1}, \beta_{n+2}) + \dots + d_E(\beta_{n+2p-1}, \beta_{n+2p}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2p}, \beta_{n+2p+1}) \\
 &\leq \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \alpha^{n+1} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \dots + \alpha^{n+2p-1} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \alpha^{n+2p} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha^3 + \dots] \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{1-\alpha} [\alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1)] \\
 &\leq \frac{\alpha^n}{1-\alpha} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq \left[\lambda + \frac{1}{1-\alpha}\right] \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2p+1}) \leq \left[\lambda + \frac{1}{1-\alpha}\right] \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \tag{3.1.4}$$

For all $n \geq 1, p \geq 1, \lambda = \frac{1+\alpha_1}{\alpha_1-1} \geq 0$

If l is even say $2p$ for $p \geq 1$, then by using rectangular inequality(3.1.2), (3.1.3) and the fact $0 < \lambda < 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2p}) &\leq d_E(\beta_{n+2p}, \beta_{n+2p-1}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2p-1}, \beta_{n+2p-2}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2p-2}, \beta_n) \\
 &\leq d_E(\beta_{n+2p-1}, \beta_{n+2p}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2p-2}, \beta_{n+2p-1}) + \dots + d_E(\beta_{n+3}, \beta_{n+2}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2}, \beta_n) \\
 &= d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2}) + d_E(\beta_{n+2}, \beta_{n+3}) + d_E(\beta_{n+3}, \beta_{n+4}) + \dots + d_E(\beta_{n+2m-2}, \beta_{n+2m-1}) \\
 &\quad + d_E(\beta_{n+2m-1}, \beta_{n+2m}) \\
 &\leq \lambda \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\quad + [\alpha^{n+2} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \alpha^{n+3} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \dots + \alpha^{n+2m-2} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \alpha^{n+2m-1} d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1)] \\
 &= \lambda \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + [\alpha^2 + \alpha^3 + \dots + \alpha^{2m-1}] \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq \lambda \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha^3 + \dots] \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \\
 &\leq \lambda \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \frac{1}{1-\alpha} [\alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1)] \\
 &\leq \lambda \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) + \frac{\alpha^n}{1-\alpha} [d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1)]
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+2p}) \leq \left[\lambda + \frac{1}{1-\alpha}\right] \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \tag{3.1.5}$$

For all $n \geq 1, m \geq 1$ and

$$\lambda = \frac{1+\alpha_1}{\alpha_1-1} \geq 0$$

From (3.1.4) and (3.1.5)

$$d_E(\beta_n, \beta_{n+l}) \leq \left[\lambda + \frac{1}{1-\alpha}\right] \alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1)$$

For all $n \geq 1, p \geq 1$ and $\lambda = \frac{1+\alpha_1}{\alpha_1-1} \geq 0$

Assume that $\theta \ll k$. Since,

$$\alpha^n d_E(\beta_0, \beta_1) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

$\{\beta_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . since $Q(X)$ is a complete subspace of X , then there exists a point $z \in Q(X) \subseteq P(X)$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \beta_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Px_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Qx_{n-1} = z$$

Also we can find $x \in X$ such that $z=Px$.

Let $\theta \ll l$ be given, we can choose natural numbers N_1 and N_2 such that $d_E(z, \beta_{n-1}) \ll \frac{\lambda_1 l}{2(\lambda_1+1)}$

For all $n > N_1$ and $d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) \ll \frac{l}{2}$

For all $n > N_2$. Let $N = \max \{N_1, N_2\}$, from (3.1.1)

$$\begin{aligned} d_E(\beta_{n-1}, z) &= d_E(Px_{n-1}, Px) \\ &\geq \alpha_1 d_E(Qx_{n-1}, Qx) + \alpha_2 d_E(Px_{n-1}, Qx_{n-1}) + \alpha_3 d_E(Px, Qx_{n-1}) + \alpha_4 d_E(Px, Qx) \\ &\geq \alpha_1 d_E(\beta_n, Qx) + \alpha_2 d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) + \alpha_3 d_E(z, \beta_n) + \alpha_4 d_E(z, Qx) \\ &\geq \alpha_1 d_E(\beta_n, Qx) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Hence } d_E(\beta_n, Qx) \leq \frac{1}{\alpha_1} d_E(\beta_{n-1}, z)$$

Using rectangular inequality

$$\begin{aligned} d_E(z, Qx) &\leq d_E(z, \beta_{n-1}) + d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) + \frac{1}{\alpha_1} d_E(\beta_{n-1}, z) \\ &\leq \left[1 + \frac{1}{\alpha_1}\right] d_E(\beta_{n-1}, z) + d_E(\beta_{n-1}, \beta_n) \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$d_E(z, Qx) \ll \frac{l}{2} + \frac{l}{2} = l$$

i.e.

$$d_E(z, Qx) = l$$

Therefore

$$Px = Qx = z$$

That is, z is a point of coincidence of P and Q . if z^* is another point of coincidence of P and Q then

$$P\gamma = Q\gamma = z^*$$

For some $\gamma \in X$ then $d_E(z, z^*) = d_E(Px, Py)$

$$\begin{aligned} d_E(z, z^*) &\geq \alpha_1 d_E(Qx, Qy) + \alpha_2 d_E(Px, Qx) + \alpha_3 d_E(Py, Qx) + \alpha_4 d_E(Py, Qy) \\ &\geq \alpha_1 d_E(z, z^*) + \alpha_2 d_E(z, z) + \alpha_3 d_E(z^*, z) + \alpha_4 d_E(z^*, z^*) \\ &\geq (\alpha_1 + \alpha_3) d_E(z, z^*) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Hence } d_E(z, z^*) \leq \frac{1}{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_3)} d_E(z, z^*)$$

Since, $\alpha_1 + \alpha_3 > 1$

Therefore, we have $d_E(z, z^*) = \theta$ i.e. $z = z^*$

P and Q have a unique point of coincidence in X .

Suppose P and Q are weakly compatible mappings, then we have

$$Pz = PQx = QPx = Qz$$

Therefore, $Pz = Qz = w$ (say)

This shows that w is another point of coincidence between P and Q .

Therefore, by the uniqueness of the point of coincidence we must have $z = w$

Hence z is a unique common fixed point of P and Q in X .

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